

Navigating the ebbs and flows of change

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Third space professionals are often responsible for promoting change in higher education, such as driving strategic education goals, redesigning curricula, or implementing new technologies. While being facilitators of change, third space professionals are also vulnerable to changes such as restructures and shifting strategic priorities, with little autonomy or agency due to the liminal position of these roles.

The fishbowl discussion for this Symposium session invited participants to speak on the panel or contribute online from across third space roles and institutions to provide a diverse range of perspectives. Topics included:

- how to maintain wellbeing, relationships, and community amid uncertainty in higher education
- the soft skills and emotional labour required to facilitate change with our key stakeholders, and
- strategies we can enact to manage the inward and outward stressors in this complex environment.

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